

Self-Awareness and Personal Responsibility among Seminary Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine what the level of self-awareness and personal responsibility among seminary students. It also investigated the correlation between self-awareness and personal responsibility. The participants were 36 students at the Major Seminary of Surya Wacana Malang. The findings of this study showed that the majority of students have a moderate level of self-awareness (81%) as well as personal responsibility (78%). In addition, the data displayed a correlation between the variables of self-awareness and personal responsibility because it has a significant level of $.01 < .05$ with a moderate degree of correlation (.426). It is recommended that the focus of seminary formation should be the development of the seminary students who demonstrate self-awareness and willingness to take responsibility for the choices they make.

Introduction

Self-awareness and personal responsibility have an important role in human life, individually and socially. Both are the basic dimensions of the human condition (Corey, 2017). Self-awareness refers to a deep understanding of one's emotions, strengths, weaknesses, needs, and drives (Goleman et al., 2019). In similar, Brooks (2018b) defines self-awareness as a clear understanding of one's character, strengths, weaknesses, beliefs, motivations, and emotions. Therefore, it is understandable that by self-awareness, humans have the potential to take or not take action; humans also have a choice to act, and therefore humans create a part of their destiny. When individuals increase their awareness of the choices available to them, they also increase their sense of personal responsibility for the consequences of these choices (Corey, 2017).

Personal responsibility here means one's belief that the person is the master of his own life, who is aware of choices and goals and is responsible for his behavior and consequences (Smithikrai et al., 2015). According to Mergler and Shield (2016), personal responsibility is a concern for self and others, fulfilling obligations, contributing to community or society, reducing suffering, and building a better world. Existentialists argue that humans are defined by their actions and are responsible for their actions (Sommers-Flanagan & Sommers-Flanagan, 2015). For example, a person who acts badly towards others will be called or defined as a bad person, as shown by the action he took or the action he demonstrated. Then, that person is responsible for the new identity as a bad person. In short, being personal means increasing awareness of my experience as the acting subject or the subject of what's going on (May, 1981). Covey (2005) states that humans act, not react like animals and robots.

Although there are theories and opinions of experts about the correlation between self-awareness and personal responsibility as mentioned above, there is limited literature that deals specifically and explicitly with the relationship between the two. Nonetheless, researchers found some articles from previous research which implicitly explained the role of self-awareness on personal responsibility. Devlin (2010) in his study, for example, stated firmly that self-awareness capacity is the initial seed for the development of a sense of personal responsibility for students in school. According to him, students will have a sense of personal responsibility for the learning process if they are aware of or know consciously their cognitive abilities and their learning concepts. Flavian (2016) added that when students are able to build a good self-awareness of the learning process, they can increase motivation, self-evaluation and improve academic achievement as well.

Students who have self-awareness of intellectual potential and can monitor, regulate and control themselves, will feel responsible for the learning process (Devlin, 2010). It was further explained that personal responsibility is closely related to awareness of and control of individual feelings and thoughts, awareness of and control over behavioral choices, computational desires or consideration of the results generated, and awareness of attention to the impact of behavior on others (Mergler, 2016). Self-awareness can also help individuals to develop positive self-regulation and build healthy interpersonal relationships with others (Erden, 2015). According to Sutton

(2016), self-awareness is seen as the main tool to reduce psychological pressure and at the same time also a way for self-development towards psychologically healthy individuals, or it can be said that self-awareness is both a tool and a goal. Furthermore, a self-aware person has a great chance of being successful not only in relationships but also in business and work because, through self-awareness, that person is able to notice his strengths and weaknesses and set goals for behaviors that can be improved upon (Najdowski, 2017).

Conversely, low self-awareness has resulted in an impact on the low personal responsibility of students in various aspects of life. For example, Ahrweller et al. (2014) in their study of three nursing schools in Germany, found that low self-awareness made nursing students pay less attention to the importance of empathy with patients when developing therapeutic relationships. Research on medical students at Haramaya University, Ethiopia, conducted by Ameer et al. (2014) showed that many do not follow BSE due to not having problems, forgetfulness, and fear of being discovered to be abnormal although it is recognized that the breast self-examination (BSE) program is important for early detection. Likewise in Jordan, it was found that the majority of students have a low level of self-awareness on the dangers of breast cancer (Alsarairh & Darawad, 2017). This is because of inadequate breast cancer knowledge, inappropriate attitudes, and low compliance to recommended BSE practices. Therefore, it is important to raise students' awareness of breast cancer and the benefits of BSE practices for early detection of this increasingly alarming disease, so that they can increase the responsibility for their health.

Thus, self-awareness can be viewed as an internal motivation that lasts long. It differs from external motivation which is the result of external pressures which are more temporary, situational, and not durable. This internal motivation of self-awareness drives a person to be proactive and responsible for this life. In this sense, self-awareness could be equated with self-knowledge. According to Oakley (2017), self-knowledge can lead people to a lifelong commitment to personal growth. The growth in self-knowledge is at the heart of human formation. Someone who is self-aware of his duties and roles in this world will exert all his thoughts and actions to achieve his life goals. In short, self-awareness is an important first step in controlling one's life, creating what individuals want and expect for a better personal future.

The major seminary of Surya Wacana Malang is an educational institution for candidates who specifically want to become missionary priests in the Society of Divine Word. As a formation institution, it has a number of rules and guidelines that bind each member must be obeyed with full awareness and responsibility. So, every member who enters this institution should realize that being a priest is a personal choice and decision. Therefore, he too, must be responsible for his choice. This means that being self-aware of the candidates of religious priests must be the pivot of their daily life wherever they are. Self-awareness becomes the main or key competence for the seminary students to be happy and cheerfully carrying out daily activities in the formation house. In other words, seminary students must pay attention and take full responsibility for any demands required from the formation house. In the seminary, he must be ready and willing to seriously commit to the daily activities related to aspects of the formation such as spiritual (prayer, meditation, Eucharist, etc.), work, community, and academic life. Besides, they should care and pay attention fully and consciously to other aspects of the formation such as psycho-emotional, vows, and health. In short, all aspects of formation in seminary must be done based on self-awareness and personal responsibility, for living based on self-awareness and carried out with full responsibility is the sign that the person is experiencing happiness by his own life choice.

We think that, in addition to filling a gap in the field, this study will also contribute to an understanding of the characteristics of seminary students regarding self-awareness and personal responsibility. On that basis, the purpose of this study was to determine what the level of self-awareness and personal responsibility of seminary students in Malang and whether there is a correlation between self-awareness and personal responsibility. The hypothesis in this study is that there is a correlation between self-awareness and personal responsibility.

Method

Research Design

The type of research used in this study was quantitative with a correlational design because the researchers wanted to assess if there is any correlation between identified variables, namely the effect of self-awareness on the personal responsibility of seminary students in Malang.

Data Collection

The data was collected by distributing instruments of self-awareness and personal responsibility to 36 students in the Major Seminary of Surya Wacana, Malang. Then, researchers conducted an interview with formators and seminary students to get more information from them to examine or confirm the data results.

The instrument used to measure self-awareness is the Self-Consciousness Scale (SCS) designed by Scheier and Carver. The SCS is a scale that measures individual differences in the aspects of personal self-awareness, public self-awareness, and social anxiety, which is organized into 22 statement items. This scale is measured in a value range of 0 to 3 where 0 = Not at all like me, 1 = A little like me, 2 = Somewhat like me, and 3 = A lot like me (Scheier & Carver, 2013). The SCS has fairly good internal consistency, with an alpha of .75 for private self-consciousness, .84 for public self-consciousness, and .79 for social anxiety. The scale also demonstrates good stability, with test-retest correlations of .76 for private, .74 for the public, and .77 for social anxiety. In the current study, researchers used a robust one-factor structure of SCS with Cronbach's alpha for this scale was at .86.

The Personal Responsibility Scale (PRS) was designed by Mergler and Shield, to measure personal responsibility. The PRS focuses on three aspects of measurement, namely, personal accountability, behavioral and emotional control, and cognitive control, which are arranged in 23 item statements. A Likert scale was used, with four (4) possible answers, namely 1 = Strongly disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, and 4 = Strongly agree (Mergler & Shield, 2016). The PRS was considered adequate, with an alpha of .81 for personal accountability, .81 for behavioral and emotional control, and .71 for cognitive control. In the current study, researchers used a robust one-factor structure of PRS with Cronbach's alpha for this scale was at .71.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed by using IBM SPSS version 20. The average of each variable, namely the self-awareness and personal responsibility of the participants, will be measured, using descriptive statistics. Then the researchers saw the relationship between self-awareness and personal responsibility using the Pearson Product Moment correlation analysis technique.

However, the requirements of the analysis through several prerequisite test processes before examining a hypothesis should be done. The prerequisite tests are the normality, heteroscedasticity, and multicollinearity tests.

Results and Discussion

Results

The results of the descriptive analysis of the two variables, namely self-awareness and personal responsibility, showed the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation values as presented in Table 1. The self-awareness variable (SA) has the lowest value of 32, the highest value is 57, and the average value is 45.19 with a standard deviation of 6.449. In the personal responsibility (PR) variable, the lowest score was 58, the highest score was 83, and the subject's average score was 68.53 with a standard deviation of 5.700.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Self-Awareness	36	32	57	45,19	6,449
Personal Responsibility	36	58	83	68,53	5,700
Valid N (listwise)	36				

The normality test in this study used the Shapiro-Wilk test as listed in Table 2. This test was conducted to determine whether the research variables have been normally distributed or not. The normality test results showed that the Self-Awareness variable has a significance of .665 and the Personal Responsibility variable was at the significance level of .327. Because the significance value of the two variables was greater than .05, it can be concluded that all data on the two variables are normally distributed, so that the data from the two variables that have been declared have passed the normality assumption test.

Table 2 Tests of Normality^c

	Class	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Self-Awareness	Class 1	,192	12	,200*	,949	12	,622
	Class 2	,300	10	,011	,872	10	,105
	Class 3	,157	12	,200*	,965	12	,856
Personal Responsibility	Class 1	,145	12	,200*	,920	12	,283
	Class 2	,224	10	,170	,920	10	,360
	Class 3	,103	12	,200*	,984	12	,995
	Class 4	,260	2	.			

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

c. Self-Awareness is constant when Class = Class 4. It has been omitted.

The results of the multicollinearity test using IBM SPSS 20 revealed that the tolerance value of self-awareness and personal responsibility variables was .818 and VIF of 1.222. The calculated tolerance value was greater than the tolerance value (.818 > .10), while the calculated VIF value was smaller than the comparable VIF value (1.222 < 10), so it can be concluded that there was no multicollinearity on the variables of self-awareness and personal responsibility.

To find out the residual inequality from one observation to another or not in the regression model requires a heteroscedasticity test. The heteroscedasticity test can be seen through the plot between residuals and the results of multiple regression (Figure 1).

Figure 1 showed the distribution of points scattered randomly, and does not form a specific pattern, but instead forms a band between the values of -2 to 2. This showed that there was no residual heteroscedasticity in the results of the regression model. So, from the results of the heteroscedasticity test, it can be said that the existing data have passed the heteroscedasticity assumption test.

Figure 1. Heteroscedasticity test

The results of data collection on 36 seminary students showed an overview of the quality of self-awareness and personal responsibility held by seminarians which are presented in Table 3 and Table 4. Table 3 showed that the majority of the seminary students were in a moderate level of self-awareness (81%), followed by high level (11%), and low level (8%). While in Table 4, it was found that the majority of the seminary students were in a moderate level of personal responsibility (78%), then high level (11%) as well as low level (11%).

Table 3. General Description of Self-Awareness Level of Seminary Students

Category	Score range	Frequency	Percentage
High	$X > 52$	4	11%
Moderate	$39 \geq X \leq 52$	29	81%
Low	$X < 39$	3	8%
Total		36	100%

The results of the Pearson Product Moment correlation analysis showed the relationship between the variable self-awareness and personal responsibility as shown in Table 5. The data showed a correlation between the variables of self-awareness and personal responsibility because it has a significant level of .01 < .05 with a moderate degree of correlation (.426).

Table 4. General Description of Personal Responsibility Level of Seminary Students

Category	Score range	Frequency	Percentage
High	$X > 74$	4	11%
Moderate	$63 \geq X \leq 74$	28	78%
Low	$X < 63$	4	11%
Total		36	100%

Table 5. Correlations

		Self-Awareness	Personal Responsibility
Self-Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	,426**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,010
	N	36	36
Personal Responsibility	Pearson Correlation	,426**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,010	
	N	36	36

** . Correlation is significant at the .05 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to determine what the level of self-awareness and personal responsibility among seminary students as well as the relationship between the two variables. The findings of this study showed that the majority of students have a moderate level of self-awareness (81%) as well as personal responsibility (78%). In an interview with formators, they acknowledged that most of the seminary students were at a moderate level of self-awareness and personal responsibility. It could be seen in their performances such as not so much eager to participate in daily prayer, meditation, work and sport. Some are lazy and undisciplined. Moreover, they lack the awareness of sense of belonging, and therefore, they lack also the sense of responsibility.

The moderate level of self-awareness among the seminary students performed that they were good enough in recognizing and understanding their thoughts, emotions, behavior, values, motivations, and goals and their impact on themselves and others. In an interview with the seminarians, they shared that they were trying to figure themselves out, concerned about their style of doing things, care enough about how they present themselves to others, self-conscious about the way they look, and concerned about what other people think of them. Some of them said that they were grateful because they have times to step back or to reflect in order to examine themselves from a distance whether they are still on the right way or track of formation to become priest. They also shared that they were aware of being valued by others (his friends) and formators at the end of the year. This is in line with what Fenigstein et al. (1975) mentioned as public self-awareness and social anxiety as one aspect of self-awareness.

Brooks (2018) explained that people who have self-awareness are people who have the ability to know themselves honestly. Those with good self-awareness have a clear understanding of their own character, their strengths, weaknesses, beliefs, motivations, and emotions. This honesty in knowing oneself makes people never deliberately ignore their failures and take the blame for others. Moreover, healthy self-awareness allows an individual to appreciate and acknowledge that there will be times where he missed the target and be honest with himself to try and strive harder to achieve goals. While according to Adams (2008), individuals who have good self-awareness are characterized by the following: being able to understand themselves, able to set life and career goals appropriately, able to build relationships with other people, able to build religious values, able to maintain a balance between the demands of self-needs with the needs of the community, and able to develop self-control of the stimulus appropriately.

While the moderate level of personal responsibility of the seminary students displayed an intentional stance of the students who are willing and ready to take action on the choice they have made and accept the consequences resulting from their actions both for themselves and for others. According to Mergler (2016), personal responsibility refers to the capacity to regulate one's own thoughts, feelings, and behavior, along with a willingness to hold oneself accountable for the choices made and the social and personal outcomes generated. In this understanding, we find four aspects of personal responsibility, namely: awareness of and control over individual thoughts and feelings; awareness of and control over behavioral choices; willingness to take

responsibility for defined behavior and the resulting impact; awareness of and concern for the impact of individual behavior on others.

In an interview with the seminary students, it was found some expressions or statements that indicated their personal responsibility of their life in formation house. One said, "I have set a goal and believe in working hard I can meet it. Other shared, "I often think of the consequences of my actions before doing something"; "I am aware enough of my behavior impacts on other people"; "When making decisions, I decide for myself what is the best thing to do"; "I treat others with respect because that is how I would like to be treated"; "My friends often make me feel emotions like anger or sadness but I can control my behavior or choose the best one to respond it".

This current study also showed that self-awareness has a positive relationship with personal responsibility. This means that the moderate self-awareness seminary students have, the moderate personal responsibility they perform, and vice versa. Therefore, it can be said that there was an influence of self-awareness on the personal responsibility of seminary students in Malang. When they were asked, "Do you agree that there is a correlation between self-awareness and personal responsibility?", most of them agreed. One seminarian said, "when I am aware that becoming a priest is my choice, therefore I am the one who should be responsible for it". Another one shared, "when I am aware that I have done something wrong, I have to be responsible for it by saying apology in front of community members". In short, they said that they always try to realize their choice becoming a priest and perform accordingly, but sometimes or even many times they loss the commitment to do in perseverance.

The results of this study proved what Rollo May stated that man is the being who can be aware of, and therefore responsible for, his existence (Corey, 2017). It was emphasized that the higher the level of human awareness of life choices, the higher the sense of personal responsibility for the consequences of the choices they make, because in essence, according to Corey, humans are the authors of life and designers of their own way of life. Sartre, a French philosopher, said: "I am my choices" (Sommers-Flanagan & Sommers-Flanagan, 2015). Covey (2005) argued that humans are the result of their choices, not nature (genes) or parenting (upbringing, environment) although these two elements are often very influential but not decisive. In line with Covey, Greenfield (2011) stated, "what we choose defines who we are". This indicates that human life is not something automatic like a growing tree, but is an attempt to realize one's potential through conscious choices and plans made by humans themselves (May, 1981). *The Constitutions of the Society of the Divine Word* (2000) says, "Growth towards human maturity occurs in a progressive deepening of self-knowledge, in the unfolding of one's personal qualities and in the achievement of that inner freedom which makes responsible decisions possible".

Donald (2019) stated that the individual is a consumer in his own world, who chooses what he wants, and in choosing, he is solely responsible for the outcomes. For example, when a person feels unhappy, he alone is responsible for it or he is the one to blame. If a person is happy, it means that person has made a good choice, uses his rationality intelligently and efficiently, and functions well in the world. Conversely, if a person is not happy, then he has made bad choices, did not use his rationality well, and did not make the decisions that were conveyed correctly. Thus, on one side, the individual is responsible for his choices, his destiny, and his steps throughout life. He controls himself and his feelings and makes good or bad choices.

On another side, according to Go (2020), every decision and action one makes is done amidst a background of available options and information, structural pressures, environmental influences, legal constraints, and personal compulsions and beliefs. It is explained that different people are influenced differently by these structural forces, each person has certain psychological propensities to act in certain ways over others, and the number of available options varies for different individuals. These disparities show off important questions to the thought of personal responsibility, namely whether those who find it hard(er) to make good choices should be held responsible for their actions. Evidently, we do not all choose from identical backdrops with equal options and circumstances.

Notwithstanding, self-awareness is still valued as the basis for the development of a person's character so that he will be better with the abilities and skills he has because self-awareness creates a will to change and greatly affects the ability to learn and stability in moving to make changes. So, self-awareness is an important first step in controlling one's life, creating or producing what individuals want and expect a better personal future. In other words, self-awareness is the root and foundation of all other human capacities (Corey, 2017), the focal point of all human development (Craig et al., 2015), or the foundation of human authenticity (George, 2015). Chappelle (2017) even asserted that the power of self-awareness should not be underestimated because a clear understanding of who we are is the foundation for all aspects of our personal and professional life. Therefore, it is recommended that the focus of seminary formation should be the development of the seminary students who demonstrate self-awareness and willingness to take responsibility for the choices they make.

Conclusion

The results of the study not only showed that the level of self-awareness and responsibility of students was moderate but also there was a positive and significant correlation between self-awareness and personal responsibility. This means that self-awareness can be viewed as one determinant factor of personal responsibility.

This may be concluded that when seminary students have good self-awareness, they can position themselves well and responsibly in their daily life and activities in the formation house as a personal commitment to his calling as a candidate of the priest in the Society of Divine Word. Thus, it can be said that the higher a person's self-awareness of his life choices, the higher his sense of personal responsibility for his choice.

Recommendations

One of the limitations of this study includes recruiting the sample from only one seminary with very few participants that might limit the generalizability of the study findings. Second, the reliance on the self-reported information of the study participants may have led to recall bias. However, being the first study to investigate this topic among such a target population in Malang will open the door for future studies in such an important field. It is also recommended to conduct this study including a large sample from different major seminaries in Indonesia.

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